

CASS Projects Open-Source Software Foundation Experiences

Daniel S. Katz, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5934-7525>
Gregory R. Watson, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8591-2441>
Elaine M. Raybourn, Sandia National Laboratories, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6987-0749>
Christian Trott, Sandia National Laboratories, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0661-5594>
Todd Gamblin, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7857-2805>
Barry Smith, Flatiron Institute, Simons Foundation, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5955-8111>
Ann Almgren, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2103-312X>
Andrew Myers, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8427-8330>

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Abstract

Open-source software projects face numerous challenges that they must overcome to survive, such as building a strong and vibrant community, assembling the resources needed to support the project's development and maintenance needs, creating a welcoming and supportive environment for contributors, and connecting with other projects that have similar goals and aspirations. Some of these challenges can be addressed by participating in a shared ecosystem of projects that are part of an open-source software foundation. In this blog post, we describe the experiences of four projects that were part of the US Department of Energy's Exascale Computing Project, and are now associated with the Consortium for the Advancement of Scientific Software, CASS. These projects have benefited from joining foundations in some common ways, such as creating a neutral home for the project and opening their governance to better support the project's developers and users. Other projects that may have an urgent need for direct funding support may not see the relative value in joining a foundation until they have resolved their immediate concern. Overall, this post aims to share experiences, so that projects can utilize this information to help them when considering joining a foundation.

1. Introduction

The US Department of Energy (DOE) supported a number of software development and maintenance projects as part of its Exascale Computing Project (ECP, <https://www.exascaleproject.org/>, [Heroux et al. 2022](#)), which ended in 2024. Because these software packages are still important to the Department of Energy, human effort is needed to sustain them so that they do not collapse ([Hinsen 2019](#)), i.e., stop working.

Starting in late 2024, the DOE funded a set of projects under the collective name Consortium for the Advancement of Scientific Software (CASS, <https://cass.community/>) to steward and advance the current and future ecosystem of scientific computing software in support of competitiveness and innovation through the advancement of science. Most of these CASS projects include funding that is distributed to software projects, most of which were previously supported by ECP, and some CASS projects address crosscutting issues.

One CASS project, the Center for Open-Source Research Software Stewardship and Advancement (CORSA, <https://corsa.center/>), has led an effort called *Pathways to Foundations*, which assists the research software ecosystem in leveraging the resources and community structure of open-source software foundations. CORSA has been working with the 43 software projects supported by CASS and a set of software foundations to provide information to the projects about the foundations and to provide simplified instructions for joining them. Additionally, CORSA has provided information to the foundations about the projects as needed.

Many of the foundations CORSA is working with have existed for many years before CORSA and CASS started, including the Apache Software Foundation (ASF, <https://www.apache.org/>), Eclipse Foundation (<https://eclipse.org/>), LF AI & Data Foundation (<https://lfaiadata.foundation/>), NumFOCUS (<https://numfocus.org/>), and Open Molecular Software Foundation (OMSF, <https://omsf.io>). Additionally, CORSA collaborates with the High Performance Software Foundation (HPSF, <https://hpsf.io>), which was established around the same time as CASS. Initially spearheaded by a number of former ECP projects, HPSF is focused on helping sustain software projects in HPC, that are developed as community efforts with multi-institutional developer teams. HPSF is part of the Linux Foundation.

CORSA has been engaging with the CASS software projects to explore their experiences with joining a foundation and whether the experience has met the project's expectations. Here, representatives of the four of the projects that joined software foundations and found it to be valuable discuss their experiences. Each project was invited to summarize their experiences, discussing their software's purpose and their project history, as well as the challenges that led to the project joining a foundation, which foundation was joined, and how this has helped.

The primary aim of this post is to share this information with the other CASS software projects, as well as any other open-source projects, so that they can make more informed decisions about joining foundations. A secondary goal includes sharing this information with DOE, which is supporting these projects through its investment in CASS.

2. Sample satisfied projects

Spack. Spack is a flexible, open-source package manager, targeted at high-performance computing (HPC). It is designed to simplify the installation and management of scientific software by supporting multiple versions, configurations, platforms, and compilers on a wide variety of systems, from laptops to the largest supercomputers in the world. Spack allows users to build software in many different ways and ensures that these different configurations can coexist on the same machine without conflicts. Spack comprises a core tool and a library of package recipes. Spack was created at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory in 2013, and it was released as an open-source project in 2014. Since then, it has grown a community of over 1,500 contributors who maintain a library of over 8,500 package recipes. From the beginning, the Spack team focused on lowering social, technical, and legal barriers to adoption and contribution. For example, to make it easier for computational scientists to contribute, the team

developed an embedded packaging DSL in Python, and added many expressive constraints for build options, flags, and features, as well as embracing customizability and multiple configurations so that users in diverse environments could collaborate and share the same package recipes. Today, Spack has become a de-facto standard and is used widely by scientists, researchers, developers, HPC facility staff, and even cloud providers. For example, it was instrumental in managing the software stack for the U.S. Exascale Computing Project (ECP), where it enabled scientists to leverage a stack of over 100 different software products with over 500 dependency libraries on a variety of different CPU and GPU architectures.

To continue to grow adoption, the Spack team wanted to remove any doubt that the project would remain open. The Spack team had received feedback from some companies that with LLNL as the single controlling organization, it was difficult for them to invest time in the project or to advertise Spack as a solution for users. Further, the team had wanted to host in-person user meetings for some time, but did not have the bandwidth to organize them. The Spack team began to talk to companies about a potential foundation, where contributors could participate in project governance. While they were interested, they felt that a large umbrella foundation would be a better option to onboard more projects. The Spack team joined with Kokkos and recruited additional projects that eventually became the founding members of the High Performance Software Foundation. Membership in HPSF has proven helpful for Spack. It led to Spack having publicly documented governance and a steering committee that can make decisions for the project. As part of HPSF, the Spack team hosted a user meeting with over 50 attendees as part of the inaugural HPSFCon 2025 and also collaborated with other projects at the conference. Spack is collaborating on HPSF's CI (continuous integration) working group to build a CI system for HPSF projects. HPSF is also assisting with logo designs, website design, and trademark policies. In the 2025 Spack User survey, 50.4% of users said that Spack's transition to Linux Foundation has given them more confidence in the project, 39% said they were not sure, and only 10.6% said it had not given them more confidence in Spack.

Kokkos. The Kokkos project is a C++ performance portability ecosystem designed to help scientific and engineering applications run efficiently across a wide variety of modern High-Performance Computing (HPC) architectures. Its core purpose is to enable developers to write their C++ code once, and then compile and execute it performantly on diverse hardware, including multi-core CPUs, and various GPUs (NVIDIA, AMD, Intel). By providing an abstraction layer, Kokkos hides the complexities of different memory hierarchies and execution resources, allowing developers to focus on scientific innovation rather than maintaining separate, architecture-specific codebases. Beyond single-source code, Kokkos aims for "best-in-class" performance by mapping its abstractions to optimized underlying backends and by providing features crucial for efficient data access. It enhances developer productivity by leveraging modern C++ features and offering an ecosystem of tools, including Kokkos Kernels for linear algebra and Kokkos Tools for profiling and debugging. Ultimately, Kokkos addresses the challenges of exascale computing by providing a robust and sustainable solution for developing high-performance, scalable applications on today's increasingly heterogeneous supercomputing platforms. Kokkos was created over a decade ago at Sandia National Laboratories, and later became part of the Exascale Computing Project which helped diversify its developer base.

Today Kokkos is primarily maintained by Sandia and Oak Ridge National Laboratories as well as CEA, the French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission.

As a multi-institutional project, Kokkos needed a neutral home for governance to encourage sustained development commitment from these (and future) institutions. Furthermore, the project needed help with managing community resources such as the website, outreach efforts and user group meetings. For these reasons, Kokkos joined HPSF as a founding member. Since then, the project has received very positive feedback from non-DOE contributors such as CEA that the move to the Linux Foundation and HPSF made it significantly easier to argue for investing resources into Kokkos. Moving from a “DOE project with friends” to being a real community-owned project strengthens the long term sustainability of the project.

The first HPSF conference, which hosted the Kokkos user group meeting, was much more professionally organized and had a lower burden on the Kokkos team than the previous user group meetings. The project hopes this professionalization will also lead to potential industry customers having a better impression of the project. The outreach effort of HPSF has also helped the project significantly. Not only has the management of social media presence by LF staff been useful, it also encouraged the team to produce more outreach material such as blogs (<https://hpsf.io/blog/>) that then are amplified by the HPSF team.

AMReX. AMReX (<https://amrex-codes.github.io/amrex/>) is a block-structured adaptive mesh refinement framework that can be used to build scalable, performance-portable simulation codes for science and engineering applications. It is written in C++17 with optional Python and Fortran interfaces and supports CPU execution as well as NVIDIA, AMD, and Intel GPUs. AMReX provides distributed containers for structured mesh and particle data on an adaptive hierarchy, linear solvers, and support for cut cell representations of complex geometries, with optional interfaces to other numerical software packages such as hypre, PETSc, and SUNDIALS. AMReX forms the basis for the spatial and temporal discretizations of a large number of application codes, spanning disciplines such as astrophysics, cosmology, plasma physics, earth systems modeling, and more.

AMReX has been committed to open source since its inception in 2017. Although historically its development has been centered in LBNL and other DOE labs, AMReX has a growing community of users and contributors at international laboratories such as CEA and DESY, as well as those in universities and private industry in the US and abroad. A desire to continue to grow this community was a key factor in the AMReX team’s choice to join HPSF. HPSF has helped formalize our governance model and development practices, which will only become more important as the project grows. In addition, the HPSFCon held in May 2025 provided the AMReX community with a platform to engage with each other in a way that hasn’t been possible since the end of ECP. Finally, HPSF has provided a venue to discuss solutions to common problems facing other like-minded projects, such as setting up CI and benchmarking systems that work on heterogeneous hardware.

PETSc. The Portable, Extensible Toolkit for Scientific computation (PETSc) provides scalable algebraic solvers, ordinary differential equation integrators, optimization algorithms, and related

software for C, C++, Fortran, and Python. It is used by over twenty simulation environments, such as Deal.II, FEniCs, Firedrake, MOOSE, and OpenFOAM. PETSc 2.0 was begun immediately upon the completion of the MPI standard in 1994 at Argonne National Laboratory (ANL).

Though scientists at ANL continue to play a major role in PETSc development, the bulk of its development now takes place at other institutions in the United States, Europe, and the Middle East. This evolution led to the PETSc community joining NumFOCUS in 2024. NumFOCUS is a nonprofit organization that has been supporting open-source software development for science since 2012. It helps with organizing project conferences, and one can also submit grant proposals through NumFOCUS, which has a very low overhead rate compared to traditional grant-writing institutions. NumFOCUS also funds projects directly through a variety of grants and hosts a yearly joint meeting for its projects. NumFOCUS maintains a Code of Conduct for its projects and has a professional team to manage any investigations that may be needed. Each project retains ownership of its trademarks, logos, and intellectual property; none of these are transferred to NumFOCUS. The PETSc community has benefited from its membership with NumFOCUS and plans to continue its involvement in the NumFOCUS community.

3. Discussion

The examples of the four projects above, which utilize two software foundations – HPSF and NumFOCUS – share some common elements, many of which could benefit other projects. These include:

- Providing a neutral home for the project, opening control and governance outside of a single institution or a single original team
- Giving current and potential users more confidence in the project and its future
- Supporting user meetings
- Helping with logo designs, website design, trademark policies, outreach, code of conduct, and related processes, etc.
- Bringing projects together to discuss common issues
- Bringing other stakeholders together to work on multiple projects in one place
- Supporting shared technical needs of its projects, e.g., examining a CI system for HPSF projects
- Accepting grants with a low overhead rate, and for NumFOCUS, using foundation-wide funds to provide some limited financial support to projects

Overall, we believe that the experiences of these CASS projects should encourage other projects to examine if or when joining a foundation would help them. We also recognize that the primary challenge many CASS projects face is sustainability, often expressed as securing funding for the project, and acknowledge that joining a foundation alone will not fully address this issue. That said, pursuing a *pathway to foundations* has served numerous software projects

across scientific communities and remains an active pursuit among projects seeking to become more sustainable.

For more information about open-source software foundations, including descriptions, a comparison, and a list of benefits, see [CORSA's foundations information](#).

References

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